

Binuclear Metal Chelates of 1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione

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Manuscript received 29 December 1995, accepted 14 May 1996

In continuation of our studies on binuclear metal complexes of polydentate and macrocyclic ligand system¹, we report here the synthesis of M_2L_2 ($M = Ni^{II}$, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) complexes of 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione (H_2L).

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes are stable, non-hygroscopic and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. Elemental analytical data of the complexes indicate 1 : 1 stoichiometry. However, the molecular weights suggest M_2L_2 composition of the complexes.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd	M p °C	Metal% Found/ (Calcd)	λ_{max} nm
H_2L	121	—	259, 366
Ni_2L_2	295	19.21 (19.79)	260, 373
Cu_2L_2	298	20.80 (21.07)	260, 370
Zn_2L_2	283	21.08 (21.55)	259, 368

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses

The electronic, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra conform to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded structure 1 of the ligand. Thus the uv absorption maxima of the complexes resemble closely with that of the free ligand (259, 366 nm)

indicating that no structural alteration of the ligand has occurred during complexation. The band at 366 nm (conjugated carbonyl functions) shows small changes in the metal complexes (Table I). The ir spectrum of the ligand shows an intense band at 1 618 (hydrogen bonded benzoyl carbonyl) and a broad band at 3 500–2 200 cm^{-1} (O–H...O functions). The band at 1 618 cm^{-1} of the ligand disappears in the spectra of all the complexes and new bands appear at

~1 570 and ~1 520 cm^{-1} presumably due to metal coordinated carbonyl stretching. Instead of the broad band of the ligand at 3 500–2 400 cm^{-1} , the spectra of the complexes show weak bands at ~3 050 and ~2 950 (aromatic C–H) and a band at ~2 850 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C–H). The two new bands observed in the spectra of the complexes at ~450 and ~425 cm^{-1} are due to ν_{M-O} vibration.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of the ligand shows two one-proton signals at δ 15.454 and 12.103 ppm assignable to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic and phenolic protons² respectively. The methylene proton signal appears at δ 4.643 ppm and the aryl protons as complex multiplet at δ 6.850–7.997 ppm. The low-field signals of the ligand disappear in the spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. The methylenic and aryl proton signals of the ligand also shifted appreciably to the low-field in the spectra of the complexes. The integrated intensities of the methylenic and aryl protons are in agreement with the $[M_2L_2]$ composition.

The base peak in the mass spectrum of the ligand at m/z 241 corresponds to the molecular ion, $(p+1)^+$. A prominent peak observed at m/z 223 is due to the elimination of water molecule from the parent ion (characteristic of the enol form³) which leads to the stable oxygen heterocyclic flavone ion radical. Other prominent peaks appearing at m/z 154, 136, 121 and 105 can easily be explained by considering the fragmentation of the flavone ion radical through a retro-Diels-Alder reaction³. The FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded mainly to confirm their binuclear nature. All the complexes show a relatively intense molecular ion peak $[(M_2L_2) + 1]^+$. Other prominent peaks are due to $[M_2L_2]^+$, $[ML]^+$ and $[L]^+$. In the low-mass region, several metal containing fragments can be located. The intensities of these peaks agree well with the natural abundance of the various isotopes of the concerned metals.

The presence of a broad band in the range 550–650 nm (λ_{max} at 628 nm) of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} complex suggests planar coordination of the metal ions⁴. The reduced magnetic moment of 1.5325 B.M. together with the appearance of bands at 798, 741 and 691 nm of the Cu^{II} complex, agrees well with the essentially planar coordination around the Cu^{2+} ions with appreciable antiferromagnetic interaction between the two metal ions.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared as reported⁵. The metal com-

NOTE

plexes were prepared by the following a general method. An aqueous solution (15 ml) of the metal(II) acetate (0.001 mol) was added to a solution of the ligand (0.001 mol) in methanol (15 ml) and refluxed for ~3 h. The solid formed on cooling to ~25° was crystallised from hot methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Molecular weight was determined by Rast method using camphor. Magnetic moment at room temperature was measured on a Gouy type balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FT IR 8107 spectrometer, electronic spectra (MeOH, ~10⁻³ M) on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃/TMS) on a Varian XL (300 MHz) instrument and the FAB mass spectra (using Argon, *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol matrix) on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 spectrometer.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (P.V.).

References

1. K. KRISHNANKUTTY and J. MICHAEL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1993, **28**, 259; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 299; K. KRISHNANKUTTY and V. T. REMA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 243.
2. U. CASELLATO, P. A. VIGATO and M. VIDALI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 31.
3. M. M. BADAWI, M. B. E. FAYEZ, T. A. BRICE and R. I. REED, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1966, 498; Q. N. PORTER and J. BALDAS, "Mass Spectrometry of Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1971.
4. L. SACCONI, F. MANI and A. BANCINI in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", ed. G. WILKINSON, Pergamon, New York, 1987, Vol. 5, pp. 221-226.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1989, p. 1194